

ASSESSMENT OF TEAM TEACHING AND ITS IMPACT IN SOCIAL STUDIES CLASSROOM

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Abstract

The paper title team teaching and its impact in social studies classroom. It performance of social studies student is not encouraging as a result of poor teaching method. Therefore, its needful to use effective teaching strategy to enhance the performance of students in social studies. It x-ray historical origin of team teaching, features of team teaching. It x-ray historical origin of team teaching, features of team teaching, personnel involved in team teaching, types or variation in team teaching, advantages and disadvantages of team teaching, team teaching and it's impact on Social Studies Classroom. Among the recommendations put forward include , Personnel to cultivate a friendly climate for effective and efficient teaching - learning process. Government should employ trained - qualified and Certificated Social Studies teachers in our schools and Colleges to boost the standard. Finally, learners should be participatory in nature in order to achieve child- centeredness in Education.

Key words: *Team Teaching, Impact, Social Studies, Classroom*

Introduction

Team teaching which is also called collaborative teaching or co-teaching is an instructional strategy in which two or more teachers are responsible for teaching a course in different methods of team teaching may be used depending on the utilized, depending on the circumstances. It boosts many pedagogical and intellectual advantages. It can help creat a dynamic and inarctive learning environmnet provide instructor with a useful way of modelling thinking within or across discipline and laos inspire new research idea and intellectual partnership (Olson, 1967).

Conceptual Classification

Dubey et al (1980) defines social studies as investigation of human activities. It studies man at home, are work, in politics, in the village, in the nation and everywhere he engages in his busy programme of living". The African Social Environmental Studies Programme (1994) States that Social Studies is the:-

”Integration of Social Sciences and humanities concepts for the purpose of promoting and practicing effective problem- solving and decision making, citizenship skills, on Social, political Economic issue and problem”

In a nutshell, Social Studies curriculum is basically designed to embrace or encourage inter-relationship among all related social science subjects.

According to Samuel Ade (2012) the nature and scope of social Studies, the current trend in our schools and the limited number of qualified teachers who teach it all point to the problem hindering the effective delivery of social education in Nigeria. A research conducted shows that more than 70% of teachers who thought the subject in 12 local government areas of Kwara State, in (1979/1980) were neither trained nor qualified.

In addition to this, Social Studies teachers, also engage in teaching single aspect of social studies that geography or history at the expense of others because they are trained in only one area of the subject. Moreover, the large number of students in our classes; the need of using audio-visual materials, including the application of child centered method of teaching, most especially the interactive and inquiry aspect of social studies curriculum made it clear that even the highly qualified social studies trained teachers are in need of team teaching to cater for the problems that may hinder learning to take place.

Olson (1967) cited in **Hillson and Hyman's (1971) pg. 84-87.**

Defines team teaching as:-

“An instructional situation where two or more teachers possessing complementary teaching skills co-operatively plan and implement the instruction for single grouping techniques to meet the particular instructional needs of the students’ Another definition provided by Richmond (1969, pg. 41). conceptualized team teaching as:-

“systematic arrangement where in several teachers with a leader and assistants, and with optimum use of technology, co-operatively instruct a group of students varying, the size of the student groups. And procedures with the purpose of instruction and spending staff time and energy in ways that will make the use of their respective competencies”

To Trump (1968, pg 40). Team teaching is perceived as :-

” An arrangement in which two or more teachers and their assistants, taking advantage of their respective competencies, plan, instruct and evaluate in one or more subject areas, a group of elementary or secondary students equivalent in size to two or more conventional classes, using variety of technical aids to teaching and learning through large group instruction, small group discussion and independent study”

A shorter and some how precise definition of team teaching is given by Sterling (1966) as “teaching where two or more teachers co-operatively formulate a plan, carry it out and evaluate its effectiveness as it relates to a specific group of students”

Historical Origin of Team Teaching

Team teaching had its origin in the U.S.A mid-1950s, but even prior to that year two or more teachers in the elementary school have worked effectively together to improve instruction. The new development probably started in the Frankling School at Lexican in (1957), as part of the program sponsored by the Harvard Graduates School of Education. In (1959), reports on the “image of the future” revealed that three (3) broad grouping of pupils might replace conventional classes and each group could have a role to play in the work school. Each period or hour located for team teaching is allotted as follows:-

- Forty percent (40%) of the time is for large group instruction of about one hundred (100) pupils, and teachers serve as specialists and a wide range of audio-visual aides
- Forty percent (40%) of the time is for small group discussion of about 12-15 pupils, and the teachers act as councilors or consultants.
- Twenty percent (20%) of the time is for individual study or in group of two (2) or three (3), and here a variety of activities would be involved such as reading, research, experimentation, writing, listening to pre-recorded tapes; viewing etc under the guidance of team members **Kochhar (2007) Collins (1989)**. In about (1960) large number of team teaching project have been tried in every section of the country and the result have been reported in professional journals. The uses of this new innovation have spread into the country of the continental world in a globalized approach of the contemporary world of education. Today more schools and teachers took up the idea.

Features of Team Teaching

According to Sterling (1966) many of teaching team are being experimented with throughout the United State of Africa and most of them have certain common features as follow:-

- Several sections, usually two to four, of a given class meet at the same hour.
- Teachers of the respective sections usually constitute the teaching team.
- Seating facilities other than the typical classroom are required either in the library, cafeteria, or the auditorium.
- Social materials and audio- visual devices are used extensively, especially during the large group presentation.

Personnel Involved in Team Teaching

As The name implies team teaching is a combination of different people working together for the realization of educational objectives and smooth delivery of instruction.

- Teachers of Respective Sections from which each team leader elected or appointed manage the activities of the team. One teacher may be good at presenting ideas while another is best at teaching the slow learners' needs. Another do well in correcting written expression e.t.c
- Special teachers to cater for the need of special learner: In normal conventional groupings where students of varied characteristics are put together in the same environment, special teachers will concentrate on those children with special needs especially those with mild and moderate hearing impairment.
- Talented citizen of the Community: The category consist of people outside the school environment who are particularly competent in artistic, intellectual or vocational, who are interested to meet the team student to provide clearer understanding of the relationship of school work to every day life.
- Audio- Visual Specialist: As the team teaching employs the use of large group instruction, where projectors and other technological devices are highly needed, specialists in the area of operating such devices are also needed into be part of the team.
- Teaching Aide or Clerical Person: this person perform clerical duties such as typing, filling, duplicating taking attendance and take care of other routine aspects of teaching such as correcting test supervising study e.t.c

In addition to the above mentioned members of team-teaching, students themselves are expected to be part of the team so as to contribute through the interactive participation for meeting the current and accepted child centered method of teaching and for the improvement of their enquiry skills.

Advantages of Team Teaching

The proponents of team teaching have supported as usage in our contemporary schools due to its greater advantages to both the teacher and students respectively. Among these advantages, as provided by Inlaw (1970, pg 41), Rotimi (1983,12(3), 17–29.) and sterling (1966) are:-

- Team teaching allows for new opportunities for teachers' participation in a co-operatives planning, pupil placement and instructional methodology.
- The teacher, as a member of the team, is watched daily by his colleagues and students, he prepares more carefully and instruct efficiently than when he is not observed by his associate.
- Teachers are also capitalized on their strength and avoid embarrassment in their weak areas.

Moreover, apart from the aforementioned advantages of team teaching to the teacher, studies shows that student also benefits tremendously in the following areas:-

- Students learn differently in a group of varying size and team teaching
- Students benefits more from the instruction by the most skillful teacher of different area of specialization.
- It provides setting for more effective students participation in the teaching and learning process. And by means of small group instruction students improve their self- directed study and independent research.

Disadvantages of Team Teaching

The opponent of team teaching gives so many reasons of avoiding its usage in schools, which lead to the emergence of its advantages as follow:-

- If a teacher is thoroughly competent in teaching his particular subject, team teaching is not necessary
- Close co-operation among team participants which if is lacking lead to misunderstanding and fruitless efforts among teachers and students alike.
- Special physical facilities and large room necessary for many team teaching situations are not in many schools.
- Per- Student cost of team teaching is some time higher than the per-students cost of conventional teaching because many team comprised. And the end result will not justify the expenditure of professional time and energy.

Team Teaching and Its Impact on Social Studies Classroom

Before examining the impact of team teaching on Social Studies classroom, it is also important to briefly bring its i.e (social studies) conceptual framework to see its i.e (team teaching) workability in Social Studies class.

Student do not all learn at the same rate, period at equal length are not appropriate for all learning situations. Educators are no longer dealing primarily with top –down transmission of the tired and ture by the mature and experienced teacher to the young, immature and inexperienced pupil in the subject classroom. Schools are moving toward the inclusion of another whole dimension of learning; the lateral transmission of every sentient member of society of what has just been discovered, invented, created, manufactured or marketed. For this, team members with different areas of expertise are invaluable.

Of course, team teaching is not the only answer to all problems' plaguing teachers, students and adminsitator. It requires planning, skilled management, willingness to risk change and even failure, humility, open mindness, imaganation and creativity. But the result are worth it.

Team work improves the quality of teaching as various experts approach the same topic from different angles: theory and practice, past and present different genders or ethnic backgorunds. Teacher strengths are combined and weaknesses are remedied. Poor teachers can be observed, critiqued and improved context by the other team members in a non threatening, supportive contxt. The evaluation done by

a team of teacher will be more insightful and balanced than the introspection and self evaluation of an individual teacher.

Working in teams spread responsibility, encourages, creativity, deepen friendship and community among teachers. Teacher complement one another. They share insights, propose new approaches and challenge assumptions. They learn new perspectives and insights, techniques and values from watching one another student enter into conversations between them as they debate, disagree with premises or conclusion, raise new questions and point out consequences. Contrasting view point encourage more active class participation and independent thinking from students, especially if there is team balance for gender, race, culture and age. Team teaching is particularly effective with older and under prepared student when its moves beyond communicating facts to tap into their life experience.

The team cuts teaching burdens and boosts morale. The presence of another teacher reduces student – teacher personality problems. In an emergency one team member can attend to the problems while the class goes on. Sharing in decision making bolsters self confidence. As teachers see the quality of teaching and learning improves their self esteem and happiness grow. This aids in recruiting and keeping faculty.

Conclusion

In conclusion to this., we can see that team teaching is a situation whereby two or more teachers plan and instruct students of varying size in a co-operative manner, involving different personnel whom their work in the team will contribute immensely toward the achievement of both intended and unintended learning experiences of the learner. The nature and scope of social studies education demand different personnel who have a different expertise to be able to team themselves in releasing the vast nature of the subject, and also to assure the involvement of students (as parts of the team) in the teaching and learning process of Social Studies education.

Recommendations

Having closely looked into team teaching and its impact in Social Studies Classroom, the Authors established that personnel should cultivate a friendly climate to ensure effective and efficient teaching learning Process. Government should try as much as possible to recruit qualified personnel to teach in our schools and colleges. Finally, team teaching should be participatory in nature. This is to say, learners should be actively involved and exposed to pedagogical skills in order to boost their morale.

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